

Four techniques to foster creativity

CRAZY IDEAS

Take a few minutes to come up with only "crazy" ideas, i.e. ideas that you think are impossible to implement. At this point, there is **no "judgement"**; therefore, you have to say all the ideas that come to you. From them we can build "realisable" ideas. Let yourself be surprised by your own ideas, they will give you clues to come up with new ideas. And remember: here, more than ever, it is forbidden to judge yourself and others. Go for "anything goes", because **the only idea that "doesn't go" is the one that is not said**. Dare to dream and imagine impossible ideas... you will have time later to put them into practice.

On the other hand, when working with your students, remember that they are responsible for implementing the ideas. So, even if you don't know how it would be possible to land them, don't worry; **it's up to them**.

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HYBRIDISATION

There are several techniques for hybridising ideas. All of them are based on choosing two or more concepts and bringing them together, creating a new or different concept.

Hybridisation can be by translation, **taking the functionality of one concept to a different one**, for example: "a bottle opener that opens pineapples"; by aggregation, adding functionalities from one concept to another, for example: "a mobile navigation app that also allows making restaurant reservations"; or by synthesis, joining the essences of two very different concepts, for example: "mobile phone cases with built-in charger (they protect and charge)".

SCAMPER

SCAMPER is the acronym for Substitute, Combine, Adapt, Modify, Purpose, Eliminate and Reorganise/Reverse. In other words, this ideation technique consists of taking an idea, product or service and asking yourself:

- What elements could be **substituted** and how?
- What elements could be **combined** and how?
- What elements could be **adapted** to a new context and how?
- Which elements could be **modified** and how?
- Which elements could be **eliminated** and what would happen?
- What would happen if the elements worked **in reverse**?

The answers to these questions will open your mind to new ideas.

SIX THINKING HATS

This technique, developed by Edward de Bono, can be used to look at challenges from six different perspectives by wearing each hat:

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- **Blue Hat:** When you are wearing the blue hat, your focus is on **managing and organizing the thinking process**. Things you can do from this hat are, for example: defining an agenda, writing summaries, or coming up with conclusions.
- **White Hat:** The white hat focuses on the **information gathering**, from an objective point of view. When you're wearing this hat, you look for "the facts, just the facts" and think about the knowledge you already have, as well as the pieces of information you are still missing. –
- **Red Hat:** The Red Hat represents **feelings and instincts**. When you're wearing this hat, you have to look at not only your feelings and fears, but also those of anybody involved in the topic you're talking about. The key here is to express any emotion without having to justify them logically.
- **Yellow Hat:** With yellow hat thinking, you have to think like an **optimist**, that is to say, explore the benefits and the positive side that could come as a result of your ideas.
- **Black Hat:** When wearing the black hat, you employ critical judgment to explore the potential **risks, concerns and problems** that may arise by carrying out your idea.
- **Green Hat:** The green hat represents **new possibilities, alternatives, and ideas**. Wearing this hat allows you to come up with new opportunities.

By considering the proposed six angles, you will be able to organize your thinking patterns, practice listening and gain in empathy when wearing the different hats, strengthen curiosity as well as critical thinking, and, finally, spark some new ideas or thoughts.

You can either use all the hats in your creative process or order them in different ways, depending on your objective. Here we provide you with some examples:

- Initial ideas, and brainstorming: Blue+ White+ Green+ Blue.
- Identifying solutions: Blue+ White+ Black+ Green+ Blue.
- Strategic planning: Blue+ Yellow+ Black+ White+ Blue+ Green+ Blue.
- Problem-solving: Blue+ White+ Green+ Red+ Yellow+ Black+ Green+ Blue.

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